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Commercial and Recreational Active UAV Fleet in the U.S. 2016-2022

The number of active commercial and residential Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in the US is crucial for both practical and research purposes. Practically, it informs regulatory oversight, safety protocols, economic impact, infrastructure planning, national security, privacy concerns, technological advancement, environmental monitoring, public perception, and emergency response. For research, it shapes safety measures, economic analysis, technological innovation, policy formation, sociological impact, urban planning, security strategies, human factors, and emergency preparedness.

Data presented in Table 1 were compiled from annual reports by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and are based on historical information from the preceding year as contained in those reports.

Table 1

Commercial and Recreational Active UAV Fleet in the U.S. (in Thousands), 2016-2022

Year	Commercial UAV Fleet			Recreational UAV Fleet			Source
	Low	Base	High	Low*	Base**	High**	
2022	328	727	727	612.2	1688.5	1688.5	FAA, 2023
2021	328	622	622	607.2	1582.2	1582.2	FAA, 2022
2020	488	488	488	1436.5	1436.5	1436.5	FAA, 2021
2019	385	385	385	1320	1320	1320	FAA, 2020
2018	277	277	277	1250	1250	1250	FAA, 2019
2017		110	110	1100	1100	1100	FAA, 2018
2016	42	42	42	1100	1100	1100	FAA, 2017

* Effective/Active fleet counts combined with multiplicity of craft ownership.

** New registration counts combined with multiplicity of craft ownership.

FAA provided a likely or base scenario together with the enormous potential embodied in the “high” scenario.

Figure 1 presents a visualization of the data.

Figure 1

Commercial and Recreational Active UAV Fleet in the U.S. (in Thousands), 2016-2022

References

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